

Appendix 2: Complete List of Meta-Requirements (MRs) and Design Principles (DPs) for Patient-Centered Pathways

Table 1. Assignment of MRs and DPs to sources from the review.

Meta-Requirement (MR) and Design Principle (DP)	P / D	Sources
MR 1: Empower patients to proliferate their knowledge, skills, and self-awareness.		1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18
DP 1.1 Provide patients with tailored healthcare information.	P	1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18
DP 1.2 Educate patients about their disease, including skill-building activities.	P	1, 2, 4, 6, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18
DP 1.3 Motivate patients to become empowered and engaged in their healthcare.	P	6
MR 2: Engage and involve patients to support their active role as co-producers of their healthcare.		1, 2, 3, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 17, 18
DP 2.1 Support patients' ability and responsibility to self-manage their disease.	P	1, 2, 3, 10, 12, 13, 14, 18
DP 2.2 Actively involve patients in care planning under consideration of their preferences.	D	1, 2, 3, 6, 10, 12, 13, 15, 18
DP 2.3 Patients and caregivers should work together to reach the best possible decision for the patient (Shared decision-making).	D	1, 2, 4, 10, 11, 12, 15, 18
DP 2.4 Involve patients in the design of healthcare services and systems.	D	10
MR 3: Provide holistic care, emphasizing the individual needs, feelings, and expectations of patients.		2, 3, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 17, 18
DP 3.1 Personalize healthcare provision in relation to patients' individual circumstances and preferences.	D	1, 2, 4, 5, 6, 8, 10, 11, 12, 14, 16
DP 3.2 Repeatedly offer patients emotional and social support, which includes recognizing family and friends as central to patients' well-being.	P	3, 5, 10, 12, 13, 14, 16, 18
DP 3.3 Provide access to caregivers, ancillary disciplines, as well as non-medical care provision.	P	3, 5, 8, 10, 12, 13
MR 4: Support caregivers in providing patient-centred care.		1, 2, 5, 7, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18
DP 4.1 Continuously train and qualify caregivers in the provision of patient-centred care.	D	2, 5, 10, 11, 12, 18
DP 4.2 Provide structures supporting caregivers in performing their everyday tasks.	P	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 17, 18
DP 4.3 Establish a patient-centred culture and working environment.	P	2, 4, 12, 15, 16, 17, 18
MR 5: Coordinate and continuously improve care to prioritize patients' needs and outcomes.		3, 4, 5, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 18
DP 5.1 Optimize and redesign processes to enhance effectivity.	D	5, 11
DP 5.2 Ensure continuity in high-quality care delivery.	D	1, 3, 4, 5, 10, 12, 13, 18
DP 5.3 Instil robust mechanisms to capture and address patients' feedback, concerns, experiences, and outcomes.	D	1, 12, 15

The design principles are marked with a “D” if they address the design process. In contrast, they are marked with a “P” if the system features or components of a patient-centered pathway are addressed. These (marked with “P”) are, therefore, commonly referenced in the development stage of the pathway design process.

Sources Included in the Systematic Literature Review (Numbering in accordance with the sources in Table 1)

- 1) Brickley *et al.* (2020)
- 2) Byrne, Baldwin and Harvey (2020)

- 3) Castro *et al.* (2016)
- 4) American Geriatrics Society Expert Panel on Person-Centered Care (2016)
- 5) Giusti *et al.* (2020)
- 6) Holmström and Röing (2010)
- 7) Langberg, Dyhr and Davidsen (2019)
- 8) Louw, Marcus and Hugo (2017)
- 9) Mead and Bower (2000)
- 10) Olson *et al.* (2021)
- 11) Robinson *et al.* (2008)
- 12) Santana *et al.* (2018)
- 13) Scholl *et al.* (2014)
- 14) Taylor, Walton and Martini (2023)
- 15) Lee *et al.* (2025)
- 16) Kim, Koo and Nam (2024)
- 17) *The British Columbia Patient-Centered Care Framework* (2015)
- 18) WHO (2007)

Full Reference List of Included Publications

- [1] Brickley, B. et al. (2020). A new model of patient-centred care for general practitioners: results of an integrative review. *Family Practice*, 37(2), 154–172. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1093/fampra/cmz063>.
- [2] Byrne, A.-L., Baldwin, A. and Harvey, C. (2020). Whose centre is it anyway? Defining person-centred care in nursing: An integrative review. *PloS One*, 15(3), e0229923. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0229923>.
- [3] Castro, E.M. et al. (2016). Patient empowerment, patient participation and patient-centeredness in hospital care: A concept analysis based on a literature review. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 99(12), 1923–1939. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2016.07.026>.
- [4] American Geriatrics Society Expert Panel on Person-Centered Care (2016). Person-Centered Care: A Definition and Essential Elements. *Journal of the American Geriatrics Society*, 64(1), 15–18. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/jgs.13866>.
- [5] Giusti, A. et al. (2020). The empirical evidence underpinning the concept and practice of person-centred care for serious illness: a systematic review. *BMJ Global Health*, 5(12), e003330. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjgh-2020-003330>.
- [6] Holmström, I. and Röing, M. (2010). The relation between patient-centeredness and patient empowerment: a discussion on concepts. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 79(2), 167–172. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2009.08.008>.
- [7] Langberg, E.M., Dyhr, L. and Davidsen, A.S. (2019). Development of the concept of patient-centredness – A systematic review. *Patient Education and Counseling*, 102(7), 1228–1236. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.pec.2019.02.023>.
- [8] Louw, J.M., Marcus, T.S. and Hugo, J.F.M. (2017). Patient- or person-centred practice in medicine? – A review of concepts. *African Journal of Primary Health Care & Family Medicine*, 9(1), e1–e7. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.4102/phcfm.v9i1.1455>.
- [9] Mead, N. and Bower, P. (2000). Patient-centredness: a conceptual framework and review of the empirical literature. *Social Science & Medicine*, 51(7), 1087–1110. Available at: [https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536\(00\)00098-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/s0277-9536(00)00098-8).
- [10] Olson, A.W. et al. (2021). Seeing the Elephant: A Systematic Scoping Review and Comparison of Patient-Centeredness Conceptualizations from Three Seminal Perspectives. *Journal of Multidisciplinary Healthcare*, 14, 973–986. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.2147/JMDH.S299765>.
- [11] Robinson, J.H. et al. (2008). Patient-centered care and adherence: definitions and applications to improve outcomes. *Journal of the American Academy of Nurse Practitioners*, 20(12), 600–607. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1745-7599.2008.00360.x>.
- [12] Santana, M.J. et al. (2018). How to practice person-centred care: A conceptual framework. *Health Expectations: An International Journal of Public Participation in Health Care and Health Policy*, 21(2), 429–440. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1111/hex.12640>.

- [13] Scholl, I. et al. (2014). An integrative model of patient-centeredness – a systematic review and concept analysis. *PloS One*, 9(9), e107828. Available at: <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0107828>.
- [14] S. Taylor, R. Walton, and A. Martini, 'Health, well-being and quality of life in aged care: Validation of theoretical domains to inform a person-centred outcomes measurement framework', *Australas J Ageing*, vol. 42, no. 1, pp. 9–19, Mar. 2023, doi: 10.1111/ajag.13133.
- [15] K. G. Lee, A. R. Gagliardi, A. K. Lofters, A. D. Pinto, and R. G. Maunder, 'Shared decision-making, the working alliance, and patient-centered care: A simultaneous concept analysis and review of the literature', *Patient Educ Couns*, vol. 141, p. 109316, Dec. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.pec.2025.109316.
- [16] E.-J. Kim, Y.-R. Koo, and I.-C. Nam, 'Patients and Healthcare Providers' Perspectives on Patient Experience Factors and a Model of Patient-Centered Care Communication: A Systematic Review', *Healthcare (Basel)*, vol. 12, no. 11, p. 1090, May 2024, doi: 10.3390/healthcare12111090.
- [17] The British Columbia Patient-Centered Care Framework (2015). British Columbia Ministry of Health. Available at: https://www.health.gov.bc.ca/library/publications/year/2015_a/pt-centred-care-framework.pdf.
- [18] World Health Organization (WHO) (2007). People-centred health care: a policy framework. World Health Organization. Available at: <https://www.who.int/publications-detail-redirect/9789290613176>.